

Analyzing the Advantages of Utilizing State Representations in a Probabilistic Reversal Learning Task

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Abstract: Cognitive flexibility is the ability to adaptively change behaviors in the face of dynamically changing circumstances. To explore the neural basis and computational account of this ability, a probabilistic reversal learning task was employed as the experimental paradigm. Recent studies suggest that a subject may utilize not only a reward history but also a “state representation” of a task to successfully solve one. However, the specific advantages or impact of state representations in task solving are still not fully understood. In this study, we investigated this matter by computer simulations, in which we used two types of reinforcement learning models, a model with state representations and one without. As a result of the simulations, we found that state representations make a learning agent robust against an increasingly difficult task, especially when the number of sampling time in each state is reduced. Based on the results, we propose a hypothesis for the acquisition process of state representations and discuss the experimental design to test it.

Keywords: Cognitive flexibility; Probabilistic reversal learning task; Reinforcement learning model; State representations

I. INTRODUCTION

The flexibility to change behaviors in the face of dynamically changing circumstances is a crucial ability for animals and humans to adapt to different environments. This ability is known as cognitive flexibility [1] [2], and its neural basis and computational accounts have been studied in many experimental and theoretical studies.

A probabilistic reversal learning task is a widely employed experimental paradigm to measure cognitive flexibility of a subject [3] [4]. In this task, a subject first learns stimulus-response or response-outcome contingencies and which of two options is given a reward and which one is not (or receives a punishment). Whether the choice of an option results in reward or not is determined by probabilities depending on each option. After successful learning, these contingencies are reversed during the task. With this procedure, we can assess the cognitive flexibility of a subject by measuring the extent to which the subject can appropriately adjust their behavior from the previously learned one. Although the task had been initially used to characterize the ability to inhibit a previously learned behavior, recent studies

demonstrate that more broad abilities contributing to cognitive flexibility can be tested with it [4].

In recent experimental studies using this paradigm, it has been suggested that a subject may utilize not only a reward history but also a “state representation” of the task, i.e., an underlying structure of the task and its appropriate partitioning into several parts, in order to successfully solve one [5] [6]. Wilson et al [5] attempted to fit the behavioral data of sham- and orbitofrontal cortex (OFC)-lesioned animals in the reversal learning task with two types of reinforcement learning model, *Q*-learning and Rescorla-Wagner model, i.e., models with or without state representations, respectively. They showed that sham- and OFC-lesioned animal behavior was well explained by the *Q*-learning and Rescorla-Wagner model respectively, and discussed the possibility that the state of the task could be represented in the OFC and that the use of state representations may contribute to flexible decision making. However, the specific advantages or impact of state representations in solving a task are still not fully understood, and neither are the difficulties of the task that are overcome by using these representations. Understanding the impact of utilizing state representations precisely may contribute

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Fig. 1. A schematic diagram of a computational model of the probabilistic reversal learning task.

to providing some computational accounts for cognitive flexibility.

In this study, we investigated the impact of state representations during probabilistic reversal learning by using computational simulations. We formulated the probabilistic reversal learning task as a two-armed bandit problem and compared the subject's behavior by two reinforcement learning models, with or without state representations, the Q -learning and Rescorla-Wagner model, respectively. The task was characterized by certain parameters regarding its difficulties. We measured accuracy, which is how much a learning agent chose an appropriate action for various difficulties. We show that state representations make an agent robust against the increasing difficulties of the task. Based on the results of simulations, we propose a hypothesis for the acquisition process of state representations and discuss an experimental design to test it.

II. METHODS

A. Probabilistic reversal learning task

The formulation of the task was as follows. A slot machine with left (L) and right-sided (R) levers was employed. The agent could choose one of the levers at each time point and get a good or bad reward, r_g or r_b , respectively ($r_g > r_b$), according to a certain probability, which depended on the lever chosen (details on how the agent made the decision will be given later). Here, r_b was typically a punishment ($r_b < 0$).

We defined as state s_1 when lever L had a probability of $p \in (0.5, 1.0)$ and when lever R had a probability of $1 - p$ for an r_g . We defined state s_2 as the reverse case of s_1 , i.e., lever L had the probability $1 - p$ and lever R p for an r_g . In state s_1 , continuing to pull lever L was an optimal choice for the agent. On the other hand, lever R was an optimal choice in s_2 . These states corresponded to the contingencies that the agent had to

learn. Furthermore, states s_1 and s_2 switched every τ number of steps. Hence, the agent needed to estimate the optimal lever from finite sampling in each state and to flexibly change the previously learned behavior as to the reversal of the contingencies. Such a two-fold problem is a characteristic of the task. A schematic diagram of the task is shown in Fig.1.

The p , τ , T and $r = (r_g, r_b)$ can be interpreted as the parameters representing the difficulties of the task. As $p \in (0.5, 1.0)$ approaches to 0.5, it is difficult to estimate which lever is an optimal choice. τ and T determine the number of times of sampling in each state and the overall times of task, respectively. Furthermore, a difference between r_g and r_b controls the ease to determine an optimal choice.

B. Reinforcement learning model

We employed two reinforcement learning models, the Rescorla-Wagner [7] and Q -learning model [8], as the learning agents. In both models, an agent learns an optimal action through trial-and-error, i.e., he/she takes an action, receives a certain reward as feedback, and updates the value for that action.

The difference between the two models is that the agent is either able to discriminate the states of the task or not. In the Q -learning model, the agent utilizes the state representations to discriminate them and then updates the $Q(s_t, a_t)$, which is the value for action a_t taken at time t in state s_t . The actions and states are defined as $a_t \in \{L, R\}$ and $s_t \in \{s_1, s_2\}$. The rule for updating $Q(s_t, a_t)$ is given by

$$Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha^{+/-} \delta_t, \quad (1)$$

$$\delta_t = r_{t+1} - Q(s_t, a_t). \quad (2)$$

Here, $r_t \in \{r_g, r_b\}$ is the reward at time t . δ_t is called the reward prediction error (RPE) and represents the error between reward r_t and the $Q(s_t, a_t)$ value. When δ_t is positive, the $Q(s_t, a_t)$ value increases following (1), otherwise decreases. For an not-selected action, the value is not updated. The $\alpha^{+/-} \in [0, 1]$ is the valence-dependent learning rate and is defined by

$$\alpha^{+/-} = \begin{cases} \alpha^+, & \delta_t \geq 0 \\ \alpha^-, & \delta_t < 0 \end{cases}. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2. Accuracies of each reinforcement learning model for different p and τ . These results were calculated by averaging the values of over 50 different initial conditions for each pair of α^+ and α^- . The four figures in the left are results from the Rescorla-Wagner model and the four figures in the right are results from the Q -learning model. In each of the four panels, from left to right, p is increased and from top to bottom, τ is increased. For all panels, the horizontal and vertical axis represents α^+ and α^- respectively.

Previous studies have shown that the agents' risk-sensitivity can be assessed by using the valence-dependent learning rate [9] and is significantly different depending on the developmental stage [10]. In terms of mathematical modelling, setting the parameters as $\alpha^+ = \alpha^-$ means that $\alpha^{+/-}$ is the same, regardless of the sign of δ_t , therefore the valence-dependent learning rate can also be regarded as a generalization which includes a usual learning rate.

As mentioned above, the Q -learning model is able to distinguish the states of the task by utilizing state representations $s_t \in \{s_1, s_2\}$. Alternatively, in the Rescorla-Wagner model, the agent is not able to discriminate between them. In other words, only one state, $s_t \in \{s_0\}$, is available in the Rescorla-Wagner model. Hence, the agent updates the $Q(s_t = s_0, a_t)$ value following the rule defined in (1).¹

In each model, decision making of the agent is stochastic, and the probability for taking action a_t in state s_t is calculated by the softmax equation

$$\pi(a|s_t) = \frac{\exp[\beta Q(s_t, a_t)]}{\sum_{a' \in \{L, R\}} \exp[\beta Q(s_t, a')]} \quad (4)$$

The parameter $\beta \in [0, \infty)$ is called the sensitivity or exploration rate. When $\beta = 0$, the decision making is completely random. As β increases, the decision making comes closer to being more deterministic.

III. RESULTS

In this section, we show the simulation results of the task assessed with the Rescorla-Wagner and Q -learning models. We compared the accuracy of actions, E , between the two models and defined it as the rate of correct actions over T , as calculated by

$$E = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} f(s_t, a_t), \quad (5)$$

¹In the formulation of the Rescorla-Wagner model, we can also define the value for action a_t as $Q(a_t)$ without the s_t state representation. In this case,

the probability for taking action a_t (defined later) is defined as $\pi(a_t)$ without s_t .

Fig. 3. Accuracies of both reinforcement learning models for different p and τ . In these graphs, α^- is fixed at 0.5. The results are calculated by averaging of over 50 different initial conditions for each parameter setting.

$$f(s_t, a_t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (s_t, a_t) = (s_1, L) \text{ or } (s_2, R) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Here (s_t, a_t) represents the pair of a state and an action at time t . As mentioned above, action L is optimal in state s_1 and R is optimal in s_2 . It is evident that E ranges from uniformly random to perfectly correct decisions, i.e., $E \in [0.5, 1.0]$.

We investigated the accuracy of the two reinforcement learning models for varying difficulties of the task, especially for p and τ . In the following results of simulations, we used $T = 1.0 \times 10^4$ as a finite number of times of sampling and $(r_g, r_b) = (1, -1)$. The exploration rate was fixed at $\beta = 50.0$.

From this comparison, we found differences between the two models relative to the increase in the task difficulty (Fig. 2). In the Rescorla-Wagner model, the accuracy significantly decreased in relation to the increase in difficulty, i.e., the parameter area, in which the model shows high accuracy, is largely reduced by the decrease of p and τ (from left to right and top to bottom in Fig. 2). On the other hand, the Q -learning model retained a high accuracy over a relatively broad area relative to the increase in difficulty. Therefore, the Rescorla-Wagner model is more vulnerable to this increase, whereas the Q -learning model is more robust. This behavior is more clearly observed by a decrease of τ rather than of p . When the task is relatively easy, $p = 0.7$ and $\tau = 1000$ (bottom right panels in Fig. 2)

Fig. 4. A typical time series of actions in both reinforcement learning models. The top and bottom panels are for the Rescorla-Wagner model and Q -learning model, respectively. The red dashed lines represent occurrences of reversals between states. The yellow characters between the red dashed lines represent correct actions at each time. The parameters are set as $p = 0.6$, $\tau = 1000$, $\alpha^+ = 0.2$, $\alpha^- = 0.2$.

both models show a high accuracy over a broad area.

For a more detailed comparison, we investigated the accuracies of both models for varying p and τ (Fig. 3). We observed a clear robustness of the Q -learning model relative to the decrease of τ , which means that the accuracy for each p (each line in each of the three panels in Fig. 3) does not change for different τ values. On the other hand, in the Rescorla-Wagner model, the accuracy shows quantitative and qualitative changes depending on the decrease of τ . As τ decreases, the accuracy decreases over the entire range of α^- . Additionally, the value of α^- which gives the maximum accuracy in each p shifts to a larger α^- . This shift means that as τ becomes shorter, the $Q(s_t, a_t)$ value of an action giving a negative RPE needs to be significantly updated to achieve high accuracy. Furthermore, in both models, a decrease of p causes a decrease in the accuracy over the entire range of α^- . In other words, even if utilizing state representations, a decrease in accuracy caused by the decrease of p cannot

be avoided in a certain finite number of times of sampling.

A more specific representation of the agent's decision making is shown in Figure 4, depicting a typical time series of actions in a later phase of a trial (Fig. 4). In the Rescorla-Wagner model, we found many inaccurate actions and delays in adaptation to state reversals, whereas considerably few errors and a more immediate adaptation to reversals were observed in the Q -learning model.

Moreover, as a common characteristic of the two models, we found an asymmetric effect between learning rates and accuracy (Fig. 2), i.e., α^+ had a relatively small effect on accuracy compared with α^- , except for a range near $\alpha^+ \approx 0$. For example, the case of $p = 0.6$ and $\tau = 1000$ of either model (bottom left panels of Fig. 2) clearly shows this characteristic, as the area, in which a high accuracy is achieved, spreads in a horizontal direction. This means that α^- needs to be more precisely controlled to achieve a high accuracy, i.e., negative RPE is a more valuable feedback to improve accuracy.

IV. DISCUSSION

We investigated the impact of utilizing state representations by comparing the behaviors of the Rescorla-Wagner and Q -learning models. Our simulations show that the Q -learning model is more robust in regard to the increase of the difficulty of the task used. The superiority of this model is, indeed, a result of using state representations with which an agent can discriminate between different states. This discrimination allows the agent to separately accumulate the $Q(s_t, a_t)$ value for every state, so that he/she can immediately adapt to the reversals, based on the values already acquired through past experiences. In the Rescorla-Wagner model, however, an agent is not able to discriminate between states and can acquire the value of only the current state. As a result, he/she has to reconstruct the value for each state in relation to every reversal and therefore an immediate adaptation is inhibited.

This superiority of the Q -learning model is more evident in regard to an increase of τ rather than p . In the Rescorla-Wagner model, the more shorter the τ becomes, the stronger it limits the number of times of sampling, whereas the Q -learning model is not limited by τ but by T . Hence, we can also hypothesize that a discrimination

between states enables the subject to reduce the number of times of sampling that one needs to estimate an optimal choice in each state.

In this study, we focused on investigating the advantages of using state representations. However, to achieve flexible decision making in the particular task or in broader situations, several cognitive and behavioral processes seem to operate simultaneously, including state discrimination, current state estimation, prediction of subsequent states, action optimization in each state, and inhibition of actions that were optimal in a previous state. These processes need to be organized in a coordinated way. Our future aim is to construct and analyze a model incorporating such processes.

While the process enabling flexible decision making, as discussed above, is clearly a hypothesis at present, we can now explain this hypothesis in some detail and discuss an experimental design to test it. This would involve the use of the discussed task with human subjects. In the beginning of the trial, subjects would not know the occurrence of the reversals (without instructions). As the trial proceeds, however, subjects would experience the reversals several times and acquire appropriate state representations to successfully solve the task. From the viewpoint of the present study, this course can be interpreted as a transition from a Rescorla-Wagner-like to a Q -learning-like learning process. Therefore, we can test this hypothesis by examining which model has a more explanatory power for each of the early and late phases of a trial. Furthermore, based on our simulation results, where we showed the vulnerability and robustness of each model against the increase in task difficulty, we can predict that an increase in the level of the difficulties of the task will increase the likelihood of the occurrence of the above-mentioned transition. The implementation of such an experiment, will provide evidence for the advantages of using state representations in flexible decision making. This will be the aim of our future work and results will be reported elsewhere.

V. CONCLUSION

We investigated the impacts of utilizing state representations in solving the probabilistic reversal learning task by computer simulations with two reinforcement learning models, the Q -learning and the Rescorla-Wagner model. Our simulation results show that state representations provide an agent with a robustness in accuracy in regard with the increasing

difficulty of a task. This is more apparent when τ , the number of times of sampling in each state, is shorter. The construction and analysis of a more inclusive model for flexible decision making as well as the assessment of the hypothesis discussed above will be the focus of our future efforts.

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